

VALUE4FARM

D2.3: Sustainable agricultural crop protocol for the Atlantic pedoclimatic region

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KEYWORDS LIST

- Smart rotation;
- Agrivoltaics;
- Biomethanation;
- Biorefinery;
- Self Sufficiency;
- Residues recycling;

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The current protocol is part of Task 2.2 within WP2 of the Value4Farm EU project, introducing a smart crop rotation suitable for the Atlantic pedoclimatic region. This setup is situated at the research station Foulumgård near the Aarhus University (AU) Viborg campus in Denmark. The protocol's adaptability and forward-thinking nature are highlighted by its compatibility with vertical agrivoltaics, optimizing renewable energy generation through green biorefinery processes and anaerobic digestion. A five-year rotation plan of both annual and perennial crops, including grass clover, spring barley, soybean, and winter wheat, addresses current agricultural challenges in the region. Wheat and barley serve as prominent trans-European crops, providing grain for human consumption and straw as a valuable fuel source. Grass clover leys contribute as cover crops, green manure, feed sources, and biogas and protein sources for biorefineries. Integrating soybeans into the rotation offers innovative opportunities, with potential dual-purpose utilization in vegetable production and biorefinery processing. The crop rotation will be assessed under different solar panel configurations, including fixed tilt and vertical, considering distance to panels, fertilization with biogas-derived digestate, and management of biomass. The novelty of this smart rotation lies in enhancing carbon sequestration, reducing chemical fertilizer use and nitrate leaching, increasing energy and food production, and aligning with farmers' needs through consultations and SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis sessions. Further refinement and extensive discussions within the AU team are still ongoing. The aim is to ensure that all pertinent details are comprehensively considered and addressed in the development of our crop protocol. These deliberations play a crucial role in advancing our overarching goal of achieving the project objectives to their utmost potential.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. ATLANTIC PEDOCLIMATIC REGION

Value4Farm focuses on tree climatic zones outlined in the Environmental Resources Management (ERM) study: Atlantic region, Central European region, and Mediterranean region. Specifically, Aarhus University (AU) examines the characteristics of the Atlantic region, encompassing countries such as Ireland, the United Kingdom, Denmark, the Netherlands, and portions of France, Germany, Belgium, Spain, and Portugal. This region experiences minimal temperature fluctuations between seasons, with summer means typically ranging between 15 and 20°C, and winter means between 1 and 7°C. Rainfall remains consistent throughout the year, with higher levels observed in mountainous areas like Scandinavia and Scotland. According to the Environmental Zones (EnZs) as the first layer of information for pedo-climatic zonation, each four climatic zones, is divided into sub regions. Europe Atlantic (AT) pedoclimatic region includes Atlantic North (ATN) and Atlantic Central (ATC). Atlantic North (ATN) includes the area under influence of the Atlantic Ocean and the North Sea, humid with rather low temperatures in summer and winter, but not extremely cold. Atlantic Central (ATC) includes the area with moderate climate where the average winter temperature does not go far below 0°C and the average summer temperatures are relatively low and this is a main agricultural production zone. Borders of regions and subregions based on Environmental Stratification of Europe is shown in Fig. 1.

Environmental Zone

- ALN - Alpine North
- BOR - Boreal
- NEM - Nemoral
- ATN - Atlantic North
- ALS - Alpine South
- CON - Continental
- ATC - Atlantic Central
- PAN - Pannonian
- LUS - Lusitanian
- ANA - Anatolian
- MDM - Mediterranean Mountains
- MDN - Mediterranean North
- MDS - Mediterranean South

Figure 1 : The Environmental Stratification of Europe (EnZs) (Metzger 2005).

Denmark lies between the Fenno-Scandinavian Mountain shield in the north and the central European mountains, including the Alps, in the south. A major soil type of Denmark proved to be coarse sand, mostly in the west of the country, whereas fine sandy clay to clay soils occupies a major part of the centre and towards the south-east. Northern parts are rich in fine sands and fine clayey sands (Adhikari, 2013). The Danish climate is temperate with precipitation evenly distributed over the year. The mean annual precipitation is 746 mm. The annual mean temperature varies from year to year, from below 6°C to 10°C, with an average of 8.3°C (1981-2010 level; 8.9°C (2006-2015 level) (World bank, 2023). Agriculture in Denmark plays a significant role in the country's economy and the utilized agricultural area of Denmark is 2.6 Mha which amounts to 61% of the country's total surface. As shown in Fig. 2 the main crops in Denmark are small grains, mainly spring barley and winter wheat, covering more than half of the agricultural area (1.3 Mha) (The Statistics Bank of Denmark, 2023). Fodder crops, mainly grass and maize for silage, amounts to 780,000 hectares, but Denmark is also an important producer of sales crops such as rape seed, sugar beets and grass seeds of various types. Vegetables and potatoes cover 60,000 hectares (The Statistics Bank of Denmark, 2023).

Biomass and energy crops are indeed important components of Danish agriculture, contributing to the country's efforts in renewable energy production and sustainability. About 36 percent or 240 PJ of the Danish energy consumption comes from renewable energy sources and of these 75 percent derives from biomass; primarily wood chips, wood pellets (mostly imported) and straw. It is a challenge that production of biomass for energy purposes may increasingly compete with food production on the arable land (IEA, 2021; Citaristi, 2022). As illustrated in Fig. 3, the total supply of renewable energy sources in 2018 is dominated by biomass (175 PJ) and wind energy (58 PJ). The share of solar energy is still relatively small (6 PJ). The overall share of bioenergy in total energy supply increased from 20.3% to 26.2% compared to 5 years earlier, while solar and wind combined increased from 7.4% to 9.6% (IEA, 2021).

Figure 2: Allocation of cultivated areas by specific crops in Denmark for the year 2023 (Source: The Statistics Bank of Denmark, 2023).

Figure 3: Total energy supply and the contribution of different energy sources in Denmark (Source: IEA (2021) World Energy Balances and Renewables Information)

1.2.OBJECTIVES OF SMART CROP ROTATION IN THE ATLANTIC PEDOCLIMATIC REGION

Through the development of this protocol and the implementation of smart crop rotation practices, our goal is to address these challenges head-on and actively contribute to their resolution within Denmark and broadly Atlantic agricultural sector:

- Achieving simultaneous production of both food and feed to enhance agricultural productivity.
- Minimizing nitrate leaching and promoting carbon sequestration for improved environmental sustainability.
- Maximizing energy production per hectare through efficient and integrated agricultural practices.
- Implementing vertical agrivoltaics installations without compromising overall crop yield.
- Attain a substantial reduction in the use of crop protection products (>40%) and external chemical fertilizers (100%) for a more sustainable and eco-friendly approach.

2. SMART CROP ROTATION FOR THE ATLANTIC PEDOCLIMATIC REGION

The smart crop rotation proposed for Denmark and the broader Atlantic pedoclimatic region, as depicted in Fig. 4, has been refined based on the input received from farmer surveys and focus group discussions during WP1 (framework and specifications). The outcomes of WP1 serve as the foundation for drafting the current protocols and this ensures that the protocols developed align closely with the practical needs and perspectives of those directly involved in agricultural practices.

This protocol embraces a judicious approach, incorporating wheat and barley as staple trans-European crops, complemented by nitrogen-fixing legumes such as soy and grass-clover. Notably, the inclusion of soy in this rotation is an innovative choice, encompassing both human consumption when harvested green as edamame and serving as a feedstock for biorefineries, as after grain pod harvesting, the green parts of the soybean plants, including leaves and stems, still contain proteins. In addition, after extracting protein from leaves and straw, the remaining plant residues, such as stems and leaves fibres,

can be utilized for biogas production. Italian ryegrass, valued for its swift establishment, is a prevalent choice in Denmark, especially in cover crop applications. The five-year rotation plan is further delineated in Table 1, highlighting the pivotal roles of these crops as main/catch crops. The technical setup for each crop employed in this rotation will be elaborated upon in the following section.

Figure 4: Foreseen smart crop rotation in Denmark.

The protocol's adaptability and forward-thinking nature are underscored by its compatibility with vertical agrivoltaics, a sustainable approach that integrates crop cultivation with solar energy production. Furthermore, the protocol is intricately designed to optimize renewable energy generation, utilizing both green biorefinery processes and anaerobic digestion. The symbiotic relationship between crops, renewable energy technologies, and environmentally conscious practices is visually presented in Fig. 6, emphasizing the holistic and integrated nature of this smart crop rotation.

Table 1: Five-year rotation plan highlighting the roles of crops as main/catch crops.

5-yr rotation, example (year 1 = 2023)		
Year	MAIN CROP	CATCH CROP
1	Grass Clover	-
2	Grass Clover	-
3	Spring Barley	Rye Grass
4	Soybean	Winter Wheat
5	Winter Wheat	Grass Clover
6	Grass Clover	-
7	Grass Clover	-
8	Spring Barley	Rye Grass
9	Soybean	Winter Wheat
10	Winter Wheat	Grass Clover

Figure 5: Diagram designed for Value4Farm depicting a symbiotic relationship between smart crop rotation and its compatibility with vertical agrivoltaics, green biorefinery processes and anaerobic digestion.

2.1. TECHNICAL SET-UP OF CROP ROTATION

2.1.1. GRASS CLOVER

Grass-clover leys hold a crucial position in the cropping systems of dairy farms in Northern Europe, with particular significance in Denmark. These leys serve a dual purpose as both cover crops and green manure, while also contributing to use as a feed source, biogas production and serving as a protein source for biorefineries. Incorporating the gas-rich green fiber fraction from grass-clover into biogas plants and utilizing the protein-rich juice (after protein precipitation) as animal fodder presents a multifaceted advantage for such biogas facilities, as illustrated in Fig. 7. Cultivated for a duration of 24 months in the designed rotation, grass-clover represents a strategic and sustainable approach in agricultural systems and contributes significantly to mitigating climate change by enhancing soil organic carbon sequestration, as noted by Soussana et al. (2010). In addition, the nitrogen-fixing ability of clover, belonging to the Fabaceae family, reduces the need for chemical inputs, as highlighted by Hansen et al. (2002).

Figure 6: Green biorefinery process upgrade by maceration (additional step for maximizing protein extraction), incorporating gas-rich green fiber fraction from grass-clover and other green biomass into biogas plants and utilization of protein (after protein precipitation) as animal fodder, with recirculation of digestate as fertilizer.

Organic arable crop rotations may have substantial inputs of nitrogen through biological N fixation (BNF) in pulses, green manures and legume-based cover crops, but nitrogen returned to the soil in crop residues by mulching and soil incorporation is often not effectively used by the subsequent crop, resulting in increased risk of nitrate leaching and N₂O emissions (Baggs et al., 2003; Doltra et al., 2015). A recent study suggested that improved nitrogen management can be achieved by harvesting cover crops and green manures, similar to straw, for silage, compost or anaerobic digestion, using the end product as fertilizer (Stinner et al., 2008). In addition, demonstrating high productivity, especially with four annual cuts designed to assess the seasonal effects of photovoltaic panels, grass-clover becomes a valuable resource for the green biorefinery, as observed in step 3 demonstrations. Furthermore, in Denmark, where significant quantities of soy feed are imported for the substantial pig production industry, there is a growing interest in re-localizing production for improved environmental sustainability, as discussed by Kamp et al. (2019). So, this novel approach involves utilizing local grass-clover mixtures with high protein productivity to co-produce pig feed, biogas, and fertilizer. This strategy aims to reduce dependency on imported soy feed and enhance the environmental sustainability of feed provision. The concept of producing protein

concentrates from grass-clover, known as leaf protein concentrate, has been studied for years. These concentrates, with protein content comparable to soy meal and a similar amino acid profile, are considered a promising alternative feed product, as indicated by Pirie (1987) and Stødkilde et al. (2018). Denmark has actively pursued the development of leaf protein concentrates from grass-clover, with various studies assessing their suitability as an alternative protein feed for monogastric animals (Santamaria-Fernandez et al., 2019). The motivation for this development extends beyond local protein production, encompassing significant agricultural and environmental benefits. The establishment of more perennial grass-clover mixtures is associated with decreased nutrient leaching, reduced pesticide usage, and increased carbon sequestration, aligning with sustainable and environmentally conscious agricultural practices (Hermansen et al., 2017).

2.1.2. SPRING BARLEY AND ITALIAN RYEGRASS

In Denmark, almost half of the cropland is cultivated with barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.), respectively 42% spring and 7% winter barley (Statistics Denmark, 2023), and this crop is expected to have an important share of cropland in the future as well. Spring barley is cultivated for two main purposes in Denmark: production of feed grain and barley malt. The latter is the preferred option from the farmers' economic perspective; therefore, their first choice is to use cultivars with a lower protein content which is more suited for malt. If they are not able to achieve the sufficient quality for malt, they will sell their harvest as fodder barley at a lower price (Niero et al., 2015).

For barley cultivation in Nordic countries, high post-harvest soil mineral N amounts of up to > 100 kg N ha⁻¹ reinforce the risk of N losses when combined with fallow periods in autumn and winter (Biernat et al., 2020). So, concerns about environmental issues in these countries regarding the water quality of freshwater bodies and the Baltic Sea, have resulted in a number of policies, including the Helsinki Commission (Helcom, 2011) Baltic Sea Action Plan (BSAP) to achieve a "good environmental status" of the Baltic Sea by 2021 (McCrackin et al., 2018). While progress has been made in reducing external nutrient inputs, with a reduction of the total N input by 11% between the reference period (1997-2003) and 2019, the threshold values set for total nitrogen were commonly failed (BSAP, 2021). Thus, further preventive measures are needed to reduce external nutrient inputs from agriculture. Reducing N input would be vital for improving N use efficiencies, with a current loss of 40% of the total N input via leaching,

gaseous emissions and runoff (Kros et al., 2018). In Denmark, numerous regulations are in place for limiting external N inputs, including crop-specific limits for the total fertilizer equivalent nitrogen rate from synthetic fertilizer and manure, the mandatory cultivation of catch crops for taking up excess soil N in autumn, and following the catch crops a mandatory reduction in the N fertilizer amount that can be applied to the succeeding crop (Aronsson et al., 2016). Grasses are often undersown in cereals in spring, while other catch crops (e.g., crucifers) are either established in the main crop via spreading before harvest, or by sowing after harvest (Vogeler et al., 2023).

In Denmark, cover crops play a crucial role in agricultural practices, particularly in spring grains, where undersowing methods are relevant. These methods often involve grasses such as perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne*), Italian ryegrass (*Lolium multiflorum*), and meadow fescue (*Festuca pratensis*), along with forage legumes like white clover (*Trifolium repens*) or red clover (*Trifolium pratense*) (Stanturf et al., 2021). Grasses efficiently uptake nutrients from the soil and prevent leaching, while legumes fix nitrogen from the air. Additionally, fast-growing annual species like oil radish (*Raphanus sativus*), white mustard (*Sinapis alba*), and phacelia (*Phacelia tanacetifolia*) are used for sowing after harvest (Liu et al., 2022). This undersowing method, especially beneficial in regions with short seasons, establishes cover crop canopies before grain harvest and aids in reducing soil nitrate content during the fallow season (Andersen and Olsen, 1993; Sørensen and Thorup-Kristensen, 1993). Italian ryegrass, known for rapid germination and robust growth, has been extensively studied and found to be effective in biomass production and nitrogen management without significantly affecting spring barley yields (Sørensen and Thorup-Kristensen, 1993). Therefore, integrating Italian ryegrass as a catch crop in the crop rotation alongside spring barley ensures both soil health and sustainable agricultural outcomes in Denmark. Cover crops harvested for biorefinery and biogas production also rely on optimal growth conditions (Stanturf et al., 2021). Cover crops are frequently harvested for biorefinery and biogas production, however the success of this endeavour relies heavily on optimizing their growth condition.

2.1.3. WINTER WHEAT

Wheat, a trans-European crop, holds a prominent position in Denmark's agriculture, ranking as the second most cultivated crop in terms of area, integrated into the country's crop rotation systems. The primary purpose of winter wheat cultivation lies in producing grain for human consumption, while its straw

finds dual utility as a valuable fuel source. Wheat contributes to the production of flour, a fundamental ingredient in various food products such as bread, pasta, and pastries and while the focal point remains on grain production for human consumption, a portion of the harvested winter wheat serves a secondary purpose as animal feed. This nutrient-rich grain becomes a vital energy source, supporting the robust livestock farming sector in Denmark. Moreover, the residual straw from winter wheat cultivation has evolved into a prized feedstock for biogas production, aligning with Denmark's commitment to renewable energy sources. Biogas, a sustainable energy solution, emerges through the anaerobic digestion of organic materials, including wheat straw. This biogas finds applications in electricity generation and as a renewable fuel, exemplifying Denmark's dedication to innovative and environmentally conscious energy practices. The significance of winter wheat, alongside with winter and spring barley in Denmark is underscored by the annual production of approximately 5.5 million tonnes of straw between 2013 and 2019, as depicted in Fig. 6 (The Statistics Bank of Denmark, 2019). This reinforces the pivotal role of having cereals like wheat and barley in the nation's agriculture, where it not only sustains food and livestock sectors but also contributes to the dynamic landscape of renewable energy production.

Figure 7: The total Danish straw production in total and for selected crops. Even a small change in the proportions between grains results in a significant variation in straw production. Each time the amount of wheat straw is changed by 1 kg per 100 kg grain, total wheat straw production in Denmark changes by 47,000 tonnes (Source: The Statistics Bank of Denmark, 2019).

2.1.4. SOYBEAN

Denmark's cool and temperate climate presents inherent challenges for soybean cultivation, as soybeans are traditionally warm season crops that prefer warmer climates. Nevertheless, integrating soybeans into the designed crop rotation represents an innovative approach. By growing soybeans for a duration of 6 months, they can be harvested to serve as vegetable soy or edamame. Additionally, the green parts of the soybean plants can be processed in a biorefinery, adding further value to the crop. This dual-purpose utilization showcases the versatility of soybeans in agricultural systems, even in climates less suited to their traditional cultivation. Vegetable soy or edamame is a soybean (*Glycine max* L. Merrill) type with larger seeds, good seed flavour and texture. Vegetable soybeans are harvested before full maturity, when pods are green and just before turning yellow, when the beans fill 80-90% of the pod (BBCH 77-79) (Moseley et al., 2021). Edamame was known first from China, as early as in the second century BC. Also in Japan, vegetable soybean has been known for more than 400 year. Nowadays, edamame is a popular food consumed in Asia and the United States (Zeipiņa et al., 2022). During the last decade, the

vegetable soybean was introduced into the diet also in the Baltic Sea region and Scandinavia. It is a valuable food due to its high protein, fat, phospholipids, phosphorus, calcium, iron, riboflavin, vitamin E, dietary fiber, and isoflavones content (Zeipiņa et al., 2022). The interest in possible cultivation of edamame plants in the North Europe region has been rising during the last years due to their high nutritional value and excellent taste properties.

From agronomic standpoint, vegetable soybean is cultivated like grain soybean, but it is harvested at an earlier developmental stage (Moseley et al., 2021). Managerial practices for grain soy cultivation may, therefore, be applicable also to vegetable soybean crops. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), for several decades, the growing region for soy excluded the Baltic States and Scandinavia. However, during the last decade its growing area has expanded towards the north, due to climate change as well as plant breeding efforts. Therefore, soybean introduction has entered the applied research agenda in the North Europe region, aimed at expanding the boundary of its cultivation area in Europe (Toleikiene et al., 2021). Table 2 and 3 present key vegetation period parameters, including sowing and harvesting dates, as well as growing degree days (GDD), for vegetable soybean cultivation at the Institute of Horticulture (LatHort). The data encompasses the years 2018 and 2019 and includes insights from both Latvia (Table 2) and Norway (Table 3). Drawing insights from the presented tables, the findings of Zeipiņa et al. (2022) underscore the promising potential of vegetable soybean cultivation in higher latitudes, particularly within the Nordic-Baltic region of Northern Europe. The study reveals that yield levels achieved in this region are comparable to those observed in other parts of the world. Notably, the research identifies hydrothermal conditions as the primary factor influencing soybean plant development. The key recommendation derived from their observations emphasizes the strategic importance of early sowing or planting, highlighting its pivotal role in achieving optimal yield levels.

Table 2 : Crop production cycle (sowing, planting, and harvesting dates and GDD) for vegetable soybean grown in LatHort during 2017-2019. Base temperature 10°C was used in GDD calculation (derived from study of Zeipiņa et al., 2022).

	2017	2018	2019
		Field-sown plants	
Sown in the field	29 May	26 June	07 June
Harvest time	03.10.	18.10.	23–30.09.
Vegetation period	127 days	124 days	107–117 days
GDD	656	785	656
		Transplanted plants	
Planted in the field *	19 June	01 June	22 May
Harvest time	10.10.	04.09.	16–21.08.
Vegetation period **	123 days	95 days	88–93 days
GDD	751	1092	651

* 3 weeks before planting seedlings were grown in greenhouse. ** calculated from the day of planting in the field.

Table 3 : Crop production cycle (sowing and harvesting dates and growing degree days (GDD)) for vegetable soybean grown in Norway in 2018 and 2019. Base temperature 10°C was used in GDD calculation (derived from study of Zeipiņa et al., 2022).

	14 May 2018	23 May 2018 pre-mulching	1 June 2018	13 May 2019
Harvest time	20 September 2018	1 October 2018	15 October 2018	xn.a.
Vegetation period	129 days	131 days	136 days	n.a.
GDD	927	888	835	n.a.
		no mulching		
Harvest time	14 September 2018	30 September 2018	12 October 2018	n.a.
Vegetation period	123 days	130 days	133 days	n.a.
GDD	909	888	824	n.a.
		post-mulching		
Harvest time	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	15 September 2019
Vegetation period	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	125 days
GDD	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	669

2.2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental arrangement of crops within the designed rotation in the agrivoltaics system (vertical configuration) is depicted in Fig. 8. The identical setup will be replicated in the conventional fixed tilt configuration. This setup is situated at the research station Foulumgård close to the AU Viborg campus (N 56°29'35.577"; E 9°33'40.266") and integrates a combination of vertical and conventional tilted bifacial

solar panels. This system is designed with a spacing of 11 m between the vertical panels and 12 m between the tilt panels, each panel strip spans a length of 23 m. Biodiversity strips at the base of the vertical photovoltaic panels are incorporated as these areas cannot be managed with machinery. Each plot within the vertical photovoltaic system is about 240 m², and for each crop there are 3 subplots ('strips'). However, as more biomass for the biorefinery will be needed, an additional share of 60 ha of experimental farmland may be used. Furthermore, 400 ha for animal feed production and the derived manure, can be considered as (nutrient) inputs to the crops in the agrivoltaic system or for additional biomass input to the subsequent anaerobic digester facility (subsystem 3). The deliberate panel spacing accommodates the planting of three rows of crops, facilitating the analysis of the impact of panel distance on microclimate, crop growth, development, and quality. Additionally, the crop plots extend beyond the solar panels by 23 m, enabling it to be used as "control" to evaluate the panels' effects on crops. In addition, the setup of the demonstration also allows for the comparison between the vertical bifacial system and the 'classical' tilted bifacial solar system with regards to crop productivity, PV-efficiency, and other indicators. The region in which the demonstration site is located experiences strong westward winds throughout the growing season, hence the application of natural (woody) shelterbelts are widely used in the traditional farmland. One of the (original) key objectives of the agrivoltaics demonstration is to investigate the effectiveness of using vertical photovoltaic panels arranged in a north-south direction as wind shelter. Detailed meteorological and microclimatic parameters are continuously collected between the panels and for the overall site, through installed flexible stations with weather sensors.

In the designed model, in each PV setup we have four dimensions under investigation: (1) crop, (2) distance to PV panels, (3) substitution of mineral fertiliser with biogas-derived digestate, and (4) removal/non-removal of straw/stem and catch crop biomass. The main strip is dedicated to crops and given the crop in the rotation (grass-clover, spring barley, soybean or winter wheat).

The sub-strip is dedicated to the investigation of crop impacts because of distance between PV panels, with three levels (western side, middle, eastern side). At an individual plot level, we are interested in assessing potential agronomic management and soil amendments, as well as possible interactions with PV panels. Each plot involves either two levels of soil amendments (mineral fertiliser or biogas-derived digestate - at equal nutrient concentrations), as well as two levels of additional biomass harvesting (e.g. stem/straw or catch crop biomass) or alternatively leaving the biomass in the field. This is to study the effects of maximising biomass output from the cropping systems. So, this setup equals 12 plots (each 3 m long) per level of main strip for each system i.e. Vertical and conventional fixed tilt solar panels.

In addition, Fig. 8 illustrates the array of meteorological nests (mobile), lysimeter ceramic suction cups or sugeceller and their cabinets, Time Domain Reflectometry (TDR), and soil sampling locations. Fig. 9 and 10 display visual examples of soil sampling and soil sensor installations conducted at AU demonstration site in February and March 2024, respectively.

Figure 6: Soil sampling conducted at Aarhus University's (AU) demonstration site in Foulum, Viborg, Denmark in February 2024.

Figure 7 : Installation of lysimeter ceramic suction cups/sugeceller and Time Domain Reflectometry (TDR) at Aarhus University's (AU) demonstration site in Foulum, Viborg, Denmark in March 2024.

2.2.1. DIGESTATE SAMPLING

During this experiment, the digestate is supplied from AU's biogas plant. The AU biogas plant, employing biogas reactor and biomethanation technologies, represents a pioneering effort to advance sustainable energy production within the agricultural sector. At its core, the concept revolves around the innovative approach of *in-situ* methanation, where the biological conversion of CO₂ to methane occurs concurrently with traditional biogas production in existing anaerobic digesters. This process harnesses the natural microbiome of anaerobic digesters to convert internally produced CO₂ to methane using exogenously added hydrogen. This results in biogas with an enriched methane content and higher calorific value, offering an alternative to separate and costly *ex situ* methanation technologies (chemical or biological). The technology developed at AU is based on *in situ* methanation, where biological methanation of H₂ occurs concurrently with conventional biogas production in existing biogas reactors.

The digestate was derived from a blend of cattle manure and paddy straw pellets. However, the objective of this experiment is to increase the proportion of plant-based sources in the digestate production process, thereby enhancing system circularity. Digestate sampling from the AU biogas plant (as shown in Fig. 11) was meticulously performed, considering the responses related to Total Ammonia Nitrogen (TAN), pH levels, and Feedstock Agitation and Mixing (FAN), thus ensuring the collection of samples that reflect the highest variation before H₂ injection. During each sampling (from 21 to 29 February 2024), 500ml of digestate was harvested and stored at -20°C for further analysis. Similarly, the digestate composition will be closely monitored after H₂ injection or biological methanation. After harvesting, all samples were sent to Eurofins laboratories in Viborg for comprehensive analysis of their composition, including Total Solids (TS), Total Nitrogen (N), Ammonium Nitrogen (NH₄-N) concentration, Phosphorus (P), Potassium (K), Sulfur (S), and pH levels. The results were used to determine the equivalences necessary to ascertain the appropriate amount of digestate required for application to each crop, replacing chemical fertilizers.

Figure 8 : Digestate sampling conducted at Aarhus University's (AU) biogas plant in Foulum, Viborg, Denmark in February 2024.

2.2.2. CROP INPUTS MANAGEMENT

Table 4 presents a general overview of managerial practices employed in the crop rotation plan for Denmark, encompassing various aspects such as field preparations, sowing and harvesting dates, fertilizer (mineral and digestate) application, irrigation, and plant protection measures. Each column provides specific details pertaining to different crops grown, including Grass Clover, Spring Barley, Soybean, Winter Wheat, and Italian Ryegrass. The setup is made in a way so that digestate application (and composition) guides the equivalent quantity of mineral fertilizer. These managerial details alongside data on crop growth (obtained through ground sampling, proximal sensing devices, or remotely sensed images), weather and soil will be combined and used in statistical and process-based crop models to

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predict crop performances during this project and are crucial for optimizing crop production, ensuring sustainability, and maintaining soil health in agricultural systems.

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Table 4: Overview of managerial practices employed in crop rotation plan for Denmark.

Managerial practices		Crops				
		Grass Clover	Spring Barley	Soybean	Winter Wheat	Italian Ryegrass
Crop (Sowing and Harvesting)	Field preparations before sowing	Field harrowing for seedbed preparation	Field harrowing for seedbed preparation	Field harrowing for seedbed preparation	Field harrowing for seedbed preparation	None
	Sowing date, amount of seeds and equipment	Late-September with ~ 35 kg/ha	Early to mid-April with ~ 150 kg/ha using Pöttinger (combi 24 cm) + Claas 640	Late-April with 119 kg/ha, using Horsch harrow + Claas 640	Late-September with 12 cm, ~ 255 kg/ha, using Pöttinger (combi 24 cm) + Claas 640	
	Harvesting dates	A total of four cuts: Late-May, Early-July, Mid-August, Late-September	Mid-August	Early-September	Mid-August	
	Harvesting procedure	Haldrup grasscutter	Haldrup Harvester. Straw and grain removing with Dronningborg 3800 (cutting width 7m)	Equipment: Haldrup grasscutter	Haldrup Harvester. Straw and grain removing with Dronningborg 3800 (cutting width 7m)	Haldrup grasscutter
	Variety of crop (specific name of the variety or mixture)	"Foragemax 49"	Not yet decided	Albat or other high-yielding, early-maturing variety for edamame production in Europe	"Champion"	Not yet decided
Fertiliser and Manure	Fertiliser amount applied (kg/ha)	Fertiliser depends on treatment. First application: 250 kg/ha NPK, Fertilisers application after the first and second cuts: 1) 300 kg/ha PatentKali, 2) 200 kg/ha NPK	Fertiliser depends on treatment.	Fertiliser depends on treatment. 300 kg/ha PatentKali	Fertiliser depends on treatment. Application of 450 kg/ha NPK (21-3-10 + Mg + S + B)	Fertiliser depends on treatment.

	Fertiliser types (specific brand and composition)	Depends on treatment PatentKali (NPK: 0-0-25 + Mg + S), (first) NPK (21-3-10 + Mg + S + B), (second) NPK (21-4-10 + S + B)	Depends on treatment	Depends on treatment. PatentKali (NPK: 0-0-25 + Mg + S)	Depends on treatment NPK (21-3-10 + Mg + S + B)	Depends on treatment
	Time of fertiliser applications	Depends on treatment. First NPK : Mid-April, Fertilisers application after first cut: PatentKali Mid-May, application after second cut: NPK : Mid-July	Depends on treatment	Depends on treatment. Early-April	Depends on treatment Mid-April	Depends on treatment
	Digestate amount applied (kg/ha)	~190 tonne/ha	~ 340 tonne/ha	~ 22 tonne/ha	~ 340 tonne/ha	-
	Digestate supply center	Biogas Plant at Aarhus University in Foulum	Biogas Plant at Aarhus University in Foulum	Biogas Plant at Aarhus University in Foulum	Biogas Plant at Aarhus University in Foulum	-
	Digestate composition (nutrients, Dry Matter, etc?)	~ NH ₄ -N, 1.33 kg/ton ; P, 0.47 kg/ton; K, 2.42 kg/ton; pH, 7.79	~ NH ₄ -N, 1.33 kg/ton ; P, 0.47 kg/ton; K, 2.42 kg/ton; pH, 7.79	~ NH ₄ -N, 1.33 kg/ton ; P, 0.47 kg/ton; K, 2.42 kg/ton; pH, 7.79	~ NH ₄ -N, 1.33 kg/ton ; P, 0.47 kg/ton; K, 2.42 kg/ton; pH, 7.79	-
Irrigation	Irrigation amount applied (mm/ha) (if needed)	If needed only 30 mm	If needed only 30 mm	If needed only 30 mm	If needed only 30 mm	If needed only 30 mm
	Irrigation date (if needed)	May-July	May-July	May-July	May-July	May-July
Plant Protection Products	Herbicide type (brand composition) and amount (L/ha or kg/ha) (if needed)	To be minimised. If needed: Fighter 480 + Penol 33 E oil	To be minimised.	Non	To be minimised.	Non
	Insecticide type (brand composition)	Non	T.B.M (tribenuron-methyl)	Non	T.B.M (tribenuron-methyl)	Non

	and amount (L/ha or kg/ha) (if needed)					
Mechanical Weeding	Weeding (if needed)	Non	Tine harrowing when needed	Tine harrowing when needed: 1) Mid-May 2) Early-June, 3) Mid-June	Tine harrowing when needed	Non
	Weeding type (machine, tool, severity)	Not relevant	Equipment: Fendt 380GT + Schmotzer	Equipment: Schmotzer1 + Fendt 380GT (3 km/h)	Equipment: Fendt 380GT + Schmotzer	
Other	Other important information			Lupin not performing well – changed to soybean in 2024		

3. NOVELTY AND FOCUS OF THE PROJECT

Considering the objectives of our current project, several innovative strategies have been implemented to enhance the efficiency and sustainability of this cycle:

Enhanced Carbon Sequestration and Reduced Chemical Fertilizers Use and Nitrate Leaching:

Through the integration of cover crops and digestate circularity, we aim to decrease reliance on chemical fertilizers and minimize nitrate leaching. Nitrogen autonomy from inclusion of N-fixing crops like clover and soya and the recycling of residues and cover crops through biogas allows a reduction in the use of mineral fertilisers. The substantial incorporation of cover/catch crops, a practice with which AU has extensive experience, ensures minimal nitrate leaching and maximizes radiation utilization throughout the year. As depicted in Fig. 8, the utilization of perennial systems in the Danish humid climate not only mitigates nitrate leaching but also boosts crop productivity, leading to increased carbon sequestration in the soil. Moreover, the utilization of digestate from biogas as fertilizer within the system promotes circularity, with its application back onto the land during crop cultivation seasons, thereby striving for nitrogen autonomy. While there remains some uncertainty regarding the fertilizing value of digestate based on plant residuals, our project includes frequent sampling from AU's biogas plant to analyse and determine fertilizer equivalences, along with precise details on rating and timing of application.

Figure from Elly M. Hansen, Aarhus University (modified).

Figure 9 : Benefits of cover crops and perennial grasses (Manevski et al., 2017).

Increased Energy and Food Production: A key innovation lies in the deployment of vertical photovoltaic panels, with a focus on assessing their impact not only on grain yields but also on straw production, cover crops, grass-clover and thus total food and energy (biomass and power) per ha. Furthermore, we are exploring the circularity of residues within the system for utilization in the biogas plant. Another innovative development involves the integration of vegetable soybeans into the agricultural system, a crop not previously incorporated into the Danish rotational scheme. This strategic decision not only aims to bolster food production but also addresses concerns regarding the susceptibility of lupins, a staple in the rotation, to diseases. Soybeans have demonstrated promising performance at AU in recent years, potentially supplanting blue lupins. Moreover, lupins in Denmark have faced challenges with diminished yields and the presence of certain toxic elements, such as quinolizidine alkaloids, as documented by Schryvers et al. (2023). Consequently, farmers have grown increasingly cautious about cultivating lupins and are apprehensive about their suitability as animal feed.

Adoption and Compliance with Farmers' Needs: Recognizing the pivotal role of farmers as end-users, our protocols have been developed based on the farmers specifications. By aligning with the challenges of the agricultural sector while simultaneously supporting renewable energy production, our approach ensures greater acceptance and compliance among farmers. Through extensive consultations and SWOT analysis sessions with farmers via Task 1.1, their concerns have been addressed and integrated into the protocol development process. SWOT analysis with farmers as focus group via Task 1.1 showed that overall, they expressed satisfaction with the potential of the smart rotation for reducing nitrogen leaching and acknowledged the additional benefits, including protein production and energy generation. They welcomed the opportunity to minimize waste and enhance circularity, ensuring suitable nutrient ratios for facility areas, and integrating agrivoltaics systems with robots for field management. Moreover, they noted the potential for agrivoltaics to align with agricultural subsidies in the future. However, they also highlighted several concerns, such as challenges in achieving self-sufficiency at different scales, logistics and placement challenges related to solar panels, biogas, and biorefining, neighbourhood impact due to increased work and transport, and risks of soil compaction and damage from tractor tracks and machinery. These factors warrant careful consideration moving forward.

By embracing these innovative strategies, our project endeavours to revolutionize agricultural practices, fostering greater efficiency, sustainability, and alignment with farmer needs in the pursuit of renewable energy production.

4. CONCLUSION

The current smart crop rotation strategy encompasses a varied selection of main and catch crops including wheat, barley, Italian ryegrass, grass-clover, and soybean, tailored for implementation in Denmark and the broader Atlantic pedoclimatic region. This approach embodies judiciousness by integrating wheat and barley as staple trans-European crops, supplemented by nitrogen-fixing legumes like soy and grass-clover. The incorporation of soy into this rotation stands out as an innovative choice, offering versatility for both human consumption as edamame and utilization as a feedstock for biorefineries. Notably, the protocol's adaptability and forward-thinking nature extend to its compatibility

with vertical agrivoltaics. Moreover, the protocol is intricately designed to optimize renewable energy generation by leveraging green biorefinery processes and anaerobic digestion. Utilization of digestate from biogas as fertilizer within the system promotes circularity, with its application back onto the land during crop cultivation seasons, thereby striving for nitrogen autonomy. Furthermore, the significant incorporation of cover and catch crops plays a vital role in maximizing carbon sequestration and radiation utilization and minimizing nitrate leaching throughout the year, which sustaining food and feed production. Further refinement and extensive discussion within the AU team are still ongoing to ensure that all pertinent details are considered and addressed comprehensively in developing our crop protocol. These deliberations are integral to our overarching goal of achieving the project objectives to their utmost potential.

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